

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Surface Chemistry and Nano-/Microstructure Engineering on Photocatalytic In₂S₃ Nanocrystals

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ADDITIONAL EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

All NCs syntheses were performed under air-free condition using Schlenk-line technique.

20 nm In₂S₃ plates: 1 mmol (0.221 g) of InCl₃ was mixed with 10 mL of OAm in a 25 mL three-neck flask under magnetic stirring. The obtained mixture was pumped with vacuum at 80

°C. After 60 min of degassing, clear transparent mixture was obtained and the solution was switch to the Ar flow followed by heating up to 220 °C with the rate of 5 °C/min. Meanwhile a sulphur solution was prepared by dissolving 1.5 mmol (0.048 g) of elemental sulphur in 5 mL of OAm under Ar flow at room temperature. The obtained transparent orange solution was injected into reaction at 220 °C resulting in graduate colour changing from colourless to orange. After 10 min of the reaction, the heating mantle was removed and the solution was cool down rapidly using the water bath. The NCs were precipitated by adding 10 mL of acetone and the solution was centrifuged at 5700 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was then discarded and the yellow precipitate was dispersed in hexane. The washing procedure was repeated using mixture of methanol/hexane to precipitate NCs and redispersed in 5 ml of hexane. It should be noted that repeating the washing step more than 2 times led to NCs aggregation. Attempts to prevent aggregation of the NCs by additionally using of OAc or DDT in the reaction did not lead to any improvement of the NCs stability but only led to a broader size distribution (Figure S1 b, c).

90 nm In₂S₃ plates: 1 mmol of InCl₃ was dissolved in 10 mL of OAm in the 25 mL flask three neck flask. Degassing at 80 °C during 60 min under magnetic stirring resulted in transparent solution. The mixture was then heated under an Argon flow. At the temperature of 220 °C the previously degassed mixture of 0.25 mL of DDT and 1.75 mL of tDDT was injected in the reaction solution and allowed to react for 10 min. The cleaning procedures were the same as in the synthesis. It's should be noted that by changing the reaction time the size of NCs could be tuned. Already after 2 min of the reaction the size of NCs was 40 nm, extending reaction time to 5 min led to increasing in size to 50 nm and to assemble the NCs into rods (Figure S2). It should be noted thiols-precursors are considered as a highly reactive and aliquots taken at the reaction time of 1 min already showed the 40 nm In₂S₃ NCs (Figure S1 a). Increasing reaction time to 5

min resulted in 50 nm In_2S_3 plates that tend to assemble and form bundles (Figure S1 b). Further increasing of the reaction time led to significant size increase up to 90 nm (Figure S1 c). It should be noted that keeping the reaction mixture at 220°C for a longer period of time resulted in increasing of the polydispersity of the samples in the case of using either S:OAm or tDDT+DDT as a source of sulphur.

Figure S1. TEM images of In_2S_3 NCs synthesised by injection of S:OAm into solution of InCl_3 along with OAm at 220 °C for 10 min (a), NCs prepared through the decomposition of InCl_3 in

OAm in the presence of sulfur powder at 220 °C for 10 min (b). In₂S₃ NCs synthesised upon introducing of OAc (b) as co-surfactant into the solution of InCl₃ in OAm at 220 °C and keeping for 10 min. In₂S₃ NCs synthesised by injection of tDDT+DDT into solution of InCl₃ along with OAm at 220 °C for 1 min. Scale-bars 50 nm

The difference between the synthesis procedure reported by Park et al is in injection step instead of one-pot synthesis which in our case led to broader size-distribution (Figure S1 b). The attempts to modify the synthesis by replacing elemental sulfur with tert-DDT which is commonly used sulfur precursor, but keeping the other parameters constant resulted in undesired increase of the NCs size (up to 90 nm, Figure S1 d). Furthermore it is well-known that thiols could introduce mid-gap traps that serve as a non-radiative recombination centers.¹ For sake of simplicity it was decided to choose 20 nm In₂S₃ plates for surface functionalization and further NCs assemble.

Figure S2. Optical photographs of In₂S₃ NCs synthesized by increasing the amount of TNM (a) to 50 µL (a), (b) to 70 µL (b) and 80 µL (c) demonstrate the effect of TNM on the synthesis. The amount of TNM leads to complete

thiolate-ligand removing that offer more active sites for creation of disulfide native bonds and induce faster aggregation process resulting in denser and shrink gel (b, c). Scale bar is the same for all photographs.

Figure S3. TEM (a, b) and HRTEM (c) images of the In_2S_3 aerogel. (b) FFT of the NCs mark as *b* and *c* in the image (c).

The hexagonal shape of the NCs is clearly visible, as well as the atomic planes. The reflexes coincide with the theoretical values for the lower order reflections of the In_2S_3 , with a structure belonging to the trigonal crystal system (space group $R\bar{3}2/c$, number 167).²⁻⁴ The indexation shown in the FFTs (Figure S3 d, e) showed that NCs share the same [001] zone axis. In the case

of NCs marked as (b), Z.A. is slightly rotated counter-clockwise with respect to (c), as it is shown with the visual aid of the dashed red line in (b) and (c) and the green arrow.

Figure S4. Band gap determination for In_2S_3 NCs and aerogel using the Tauc plot for the data obtained from UV-VIS-NIR spectroscopy

Figure S5. Chronoamperometric characteristics normalized by the amount of material onto substrate at 0.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl (b) obtained for xerogel layers produced from MUA-NC sol with concentration: 20 mg/mL; 50 mg/mL and 100 mg/mL. The total mass of the material onto substrate was determined by ICP measurements.

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